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GGOS Days 2022

Minutes

November 14-15, 2022

Munich, Germany

IUGG

Global Geodetic
Observing System

GGOS Days 2022

Minutes

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1 Summary

GGOS organized the annual GGOS Days this year at November 14-15, 2022 in Munich (Germany) as a hybrid meeting at the **Bavarian Academy of Science and Humanities (BAW)** in the Residenz. In total 111 interested people participated in this conference. 33 of them in-person and 78 virtually. The GGOS Days 2022 meeting was locally organized by the **DGK** (German Geodetic Commission), the **BAW** (Bavarian Academy of Science and Humanities) and the **TUM** (Technical University of Munich).

The conference started with an **Opening Session** with presentations on DGK, IAG and GGOS. It was followed by the **Keynote Speaker Session** with presentations covering novel geodetic technologies and procedures as well as contributions of geodesy to climate change processes. In addition, all **GGOS components reported** on their recent activities and presented their plans for the coming year. It includes the two GGOS Bureaus,

the three GGOS Focus Areas, the two GGOS Affiliates, the GGOS Science Panel, the GGOS Coordinating Office as well as the GGOS Committees and the GGOS Working Groups. The GGOS Days also provided space for fruitful discussions. All in all, this conference was very successful.

The participants and the topics to be addressed during the individual meetings are indicated in the agenda given below.

Directly after the GGOS Days 2022 the [GGOS Strategic Plan Workshop](#) was convened at the same venue. Key people within GGOS and IAG discussed together with invited IAG Service representatives the future direction and goals of GGOS. The discussion was based on the results of a community survey to develop a new strategy of GGOS.

Entrance door

2 General Information

Date / Time: **November 14-15, 2022 | 08:30 – 17:30 CET (Europe)**
Official Website: <https://ggos.org/event/ggos-days-2022/>
Venue: **Bavarian Academy of Science and Humanities (BAdW) at Residenz**
Address: [Alfons-Goppel-Straße 11, 80539 Munich, Germany](#)

3 Documents, Photos, Videos - Download

Status Reports of GGOS components: at [GGOS Cloud](#) or at [Zenodo Platforms](#) (with DOI's)

- GGOS Bureau of Networks and Observations [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7313064](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7313064)
- GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7298661](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7298661)
- GGOS Focus Area “Unified Height System” [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7298702](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7298702)
- GGOS Focus Area “Geodetic Space Weather Research” [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7298694](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7298694)

Presentation Slides: at [Zenodo Platforms](#) with DOI's (or at [GGOS Cloud](#))

Photos of the Conference: <https://cloud.ggos.org/index.php/s/SGaW7fiXM3gCZtT>

Videos – Recording of whole Conference at YouTube - [GGOS Days 2022 Playlist](#)

- **Day 1:** Please watch here: <https://youtu.be/pkKQZaLdtnA>
- **Day 2:** Please watch here: <https://youtu.be/zGrLhZT1vY>

4 Meeting Organization

Chair: Basara Miyahara

Local Organizer: Detlef Angermann, Urs Hugentobler, Laura Sánchez, Michael Schmidt, Felix Müller, Stefanie Daurer, Julia Schießl

GGOS Organizer: Martin Sehnal, Detlef Angermann, Laura Sánchez, Basara Miyahara

5 Schedule

Day 1 - Monday, November 14

Time	Theme	Presenter	Presentation Slides - DOI
08:30 – 10:00	<u>Opening Session</u>	Chair: Urs Hugentobler, Harald Schuh	Video
5 min.	GGOS Days Opening	Basara Miyahara	Video
10 min.	Welcome to the GGOS Days 2022	Detlef Angermann	Video
10 min.	Welcome at Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities - BAdW	Arndt Bode	Video
20 min.	The German Geodetic Commission (DGK) and its Contribution to GGOS	Harald Schuh	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7324528 Video
20 min.	IAG and GGOS: Future Challenges	Zuheir Altamimi	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7372932 Video
20 min.	GGOS report	Basara Miyahara	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7336398 Video

10:00 – 10:30: Coffee Break

Time	Theme	Presenter	Presentation Slides - DOI
10:30 – 12:10	<u>Keynote Speaker Session (Invited Presentations)</u>	Chair: Harald Schuh	
20 min.	Novel Sensors and Quantum Technology for Geodesy	Jürgen Müller (<i>remotely</i>)	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7319051 Video
20 min.	Satellite Gravity Missions	Roland Pail	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7303559 Video
20 min.	GENESIS: Co-location of Geodetic Techniques in Space	Markus Rothacher	Video
20 min.	Combination of satellite remote sensing with glaciological and geodetic field methods for the study of mountain glaciers	Anja Wendt, Christof Völksen, Christoph Mayer, Christian Gerlach, Martin Rückamp, BAdW	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7327257 Video
20 min.	The ice sheets' contribution to sea level rise	Martin Horwarth (<i>remotely</i>)	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7333390 Video

12:10 – 14:00: Lunch Break

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Time	Theme	Presenter	Presentation Slides - DOI
14:00 – 15:30	<u>GGOS Internal Activities</u>	Chair: Basara Miyahara	
15 min.	GGOS D-A-CH – Status Report	Hansjörg Kutterer	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7326228 Video
15 min.	Report from GGOS Japan	Basara Miyahara, Yosuke Yokota (<i>remotely</i>), Toshimichi Otsubo	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7327985 Video
15 min.	GGOS Iberoatlantic: Towards a new GGOS affiliate	Esther Azcue, José López-Fernández, José Manuel Ferrándiz	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7341749 Video
10 min.	GGOS Science Panel – Activities in 2021-2022	Kosuke Heki (<i>remotely</i>)	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7374819 Video
15 min.	WG on “DOIs for Geodetic Data Sets” – Backgrounds about DOI minting	Kirsten Elger	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7354893 Video
10 min.	GGOS Days 2023 - Yebes	José López-Fernández, Esther Azcue, José Manuel Ferrándiz	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7341901 Video

15:30 – 16:00: Coffee Break

Time	Theme	Presenter	Presentation Slides - DOI
16:00 – 17:30	<u>GGOS External Activities</u>	Chair: Laura Sánchez	
20 min.	GGOS Coordinating Office – Outreach & Education	Martin Sehnal	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7321807 Video
20 min.	GGOS External Relations Update	Allison Craddock	Video
20 min.	United Nations Global Geodetic Centre of Excellence in Bonn	Jan Dostal	Video
20 min.	GGOS Portal - Revival of a Metadata Platform	Martin Sehnal	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7321835 Video
10 min.	General discussion / Any other Business	all	

19:00 – 22:00: Social Event at a Bavarian restaurant “Andechser am Dom”

Day 2 - Tuesday, November 15

Time	Theme	Presenter	Presentation Slides - DOI
08:30 – 09:15	GGOS Focus Areas “Unified Height System”	Chair: Laura Sánchez	
45 min.	Report of the Focus Area	Laura Sánchez	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7376460 Video
09:15 – 10:00	GGOS Focus Areas “Geodetic Space Weather Research”	Chair: Michael Schmidt	
	Report of the Focus Area	Michael Schmidt	Video
	Imaging the 3D Ionosphere by Global Scale Tomography	Fabricio Prol (<i>remotely</i>)	Video
	Increasing the application of space-borne measurements for predicting multi-level global thermospheric neutral density	Ehsan Forootan (<i>remotely</i>)	Video

10:00 – 10:30: Coffee Break

Time	Theme	Presenter	Presentation Slides
10:30 – 12:00	GGOS Bureau of Products and Standards	Chair: Detlef Angermann	
	Report of the Bureau	Detlef Angermann	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7341637 Video
	WG: Towards a consistent set of parameters for the definition of a new GRS	Urs Marti (<i>remotely</i>)	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7324183 Video
	GGOS Committee “Contributions to Earth System Modeling”	Maik Thomas, Detlef Angermann	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7347730 Video
	Definition of Essential Geodetic Variables (EGVs)	Richard Gross	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7325702 Video

12:00 – 14:00: Lunch Break

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Time	Theme	Presenter	Presentation Slides - DOI
14:00 – 15:30	GGOS Bureau of Networks and Observations	Chair: Martin Sehnal	
	Introduction into the Bureau	Michael Pearlman <i>(remotely)</i>	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7341176
	GGOS Standing Committee PLATO	Daniela Thaller	Video
	Update on the IVS	Rüdiger Haas	Video
	Update on the ILRS	Michael Pearlman <i>(remotely)</i>	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7341237 Video
	The IGS Infrastructure: Current Status and Future Plans	Markus Bradke <i>(remotely)</i>	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7333613 Video
	DORIS Network Status	Jérôme Saunier <i>(remotely)</i>	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7331044 Video
	Update on the activities of the International Gravity Field Services	Georgios Vergos <i>(remotely)</i>	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7337355 Video
	The Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level – Nearly 90 years of service	Elizabeth Bradshaw <i>(remotely)</i>	Video

15:30 – 16:00: Coffee Break

Time	Theme	Presenter	Presentation Slides - DOI
16.00 – 16:45	GGOS Focus Areas “Geohazards”	Chair: Martin Sehnal	
	Report of the Focus Area	John LaBrecque <i>(remotely)</i>	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7327858 Video
16.45 – 17:30	General discussion / Any other Business	Chair: Basara Miyahara	Video

6 Participants

Members of the GGOS Consortium, GGOS Coordinating Board, GGOS Bureaus, GGOS Focus Areas, GGOS Science Panel, invited guests and all interested persons were highly welcome to attend the GGOS Days 2022.

111 Participants (33 in-person and 78 virtual)

Group photo of in-person participants 1 (Day 2)

Group photo of some virtual participants (Day 2 – afternoon)

33 In-Person Participants:

Name	Country of Work
Johannes Böhm	Austria
Martin Sehnal	Austria
Markku Poutanen	Finland
Zuheir Altamimi	France
Alexander Kehm	Germany
Anja Wendt	Germany
Arndt Bode	Germany
Christof Völksen	Germany
Daniela Thaller	Germany
Detlef Angermann	Germany
Hansjörg Kutterer	Germany
Harald Schuh	Germany
Hermann Drewes	Germany
Jan Dostal	Germany
Julia Schießl	Germany
Kirsten Elger	Germany
Laura Sanchez	Germany
Manuela Seitz	Germany
Michael Schmidt	Germany
Roland Pail	Germany
Sergei Rudenko	Germany
Susanne Glaser	Germany
Thomas Gruber	Germany
Basara Miyahara	Japan
Luisa Moniz	Portugal
Roelf Botha	South Africa
Esther Azcue	Spain
Jose Antonio Lopez Fernandez	Spain
Jose M. Ferrandiz	Spain
Julia Koch	Switzerland
Markus Rothacher	Switzerland
Allison Craddock	USA
Richard Gross	USA

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78 Virtual Participants:

Name	Country of Work
Claudia noemi Tocho	Argentina
Ezequiel D. Antokoletz	Argentina
Maria Eugenia Gomez	Argentina
Anna Riddell	Australia
Ryan Ruddick	Australia
Roberto Teixeira Luz	Brazil
Lyubka Pashova	Bulgaria
Jianliang Huang	Canada
Philippe Lamothe	Canada
José Antonio Tarrío	Chile
Kosuke Heki	China
Diego Cortes	Colombia
Ehsan Forootan	Denmark
Fabrizio Prol	Finland
Jaakko Mäkinen	Finland
EXERTIER Pierre	France
Jérôme SAUNIER	France
Laurent Soudarin	France
Denise Dettmering	Germany
Elmas Sinem Ince	Germany
Felix Müller	Germany
Florian Seitz	Germany
Jürgen Müller	Germany
Markus Bradke	Germany
Martin Horwath	Germany
Mohammad Mohseni Aref	Germany
Peter Steigenberger	Germany
Qing Liu	Germany
Robert Heinkelmann	Germany
Shrishail Raut	Germany
Sujata Dhar	Germany
Tilo Schöne	Germany
Dimitris Anastasiou	Greece
George Vergos	Greece
Arnab Laha	India

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Shivangi Singh	India
Riccardo Barzaghi	Italy
Vincenza Tornatore	Italy
Toshimichi Otsubo	Japan
Yusuke Yokota	Japan
Yuto Nakamura	Japan
JANIS KAMINSKIS	Latvia
Helena Ribeiro	Portugal
João Salmim Ferreira	Portugal
Manuela Vasconcelos	Portugal
Aletha de Witt	South Africa
Glenda Coetzer	South Africa
Marisa Nickola	South Africa
Hasu Yoon	South Korea
YoungJin LEE	South Korea
Andrea Rosillo Sánchez	Spain
Elena Martínez Sanchez	Spain
José C. Rodríguez	Spain
José Manuel Serna	Spain
Leonor Cui Domingo Centeno	Spain
Víctor Puente	Spain
Rüdiger Haas	Sweden
Benedikt Soja	Switzerland
Urs Marti	Switzerland
Arnessa Gooding	Trinidad and Tobago
Aydın Üstün	Turkey
Emine TANIR KAYIKÇI	Turkey
Hüseyin Mercan	Turkey
Metehan Uz	Turkey
Orhan Akyilmaz	Turkey
Andy Matthews	United Kingdom
Elizabeth Bradshaw	United Kingdom
Erricos C. Pavlis	USA
John Labrecque	USA
Michael Pearlman	USA
Ryan Hippenstiel	USA
Cornelis	N/K

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Diogo Avelar	N/K
Francisco Wallenstein	N/K
Mariana Moreira	N/K
Miguel González	N/K
Sevda Olgun	N/K
Taegyu Ahn	N/K